

ISic0962

I.Sicily inscription 0962

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 104

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140463

1. μηνὶ Νοβεν-
2. βρίῳ ἐτελεύ-
3. τησεν Ῥό-
4. δων πρ (ὀ) θ'
5. καλανδῶν
6. Δεκενβρί-
7. ων ἡμέρα
8. Ἡλίου.
9. ²vs. 3, ex.:² □c ²⁶Χρ(ιστό)ς²⁶
- 10.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492612

EDCS 39102139

PHI 140463

Bibliography

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